

The Rise of Startup Culture: A Step Towards the Self-Reliant Nation

Dr. Siddharth Shrihari Maske

Dept. of English, Government Arts and Commerce College, Ahwa (Dang),

Near Govt. ITI, Tq. Ahwa, Dist. Dang Pin Code: 394710 (Gujarat)

Corresponding Author – Dr. Siddharth Shrihari Maske

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Abstract:

India has developed extensive systems for startups, with policies, youth potential, and digitalization. Various policies, such as Startup India, Stand-Up India, and Atal Innovation, have been implemented and publicized to prioritize encouragement and support for startups. Indian youths have faced challenges such as limited overseas opportunities due to policies made by foreign countries, and startup initiatives will help fill the gap. Primarily, it is the ultimate goal to provide opportunities, solve everyday problems, provide a solid platform for the talent, and make the youth self-reliant. In the present time, it becomes one of the major countries for inspiring and providing a strong base for startups and innovation. In relation to this Indian government is providing funds for the startups. The present paper deals with the emergence of startup culture in India and its development. It further talks about the significance of startups in developing countries like India and the role of higher education. It also addresses the necessity of the required mindset for the startup network amongst the masses. The startup culture attracts innovation as well as technological advancement, and that can pave the way for global investment.

Keywords: Startup, Development, Innovation, Entrepreneur.

Introduction:

The rapid development of industries, the invention of the railway, and the electric telegraph gave rise to startups during the Victorian period. Many people started small-scale industries, family businesses, and partnerships, as wealthy and technical experts slowly emerged due to high profits and innovation. The term 'start-up' was coined by the economist Joseph Schumpeter to describe the high profitability and risk of businesses compared to traditional forms of enterprise (Vats 99). During the Second World War in America, where innovative ideas and technological advances provided a platform for new businesses, the emergence of start-ups was considered. In the 1980s and 1990s, an economic crisis created opportunities for new businesses (99). The invention of computers and the internet

helped new entrepreneurs to venture into this emerging field of business. In 1976, Steve Jobs and Steve Wozniak, who started Apple in a garage in California, is considered the first start-up. Later, in the 1990s, many online companies emerged and became successful (Pekevski 70). To raise awareness of start-ups, several programmes, events, and conferences have been organised worldwide, from Montreal to Turin, Finland to Namibia, England, and the United States of America. This shows that start-ups are now present all over the world.

Initiatives to Promote Startups India:

The Indian government has also taken initiatives to promote startups, such as Startup India, Atmanirbhar Bharat, and Make in India. One of the major projects, Startup India, has been

launched to create a strong ecosystem for innovation and entrepreneurs (Startup India). Prime Minister Shri. Narendra Modi's vision behind the Promotion and implementation of Atmanirbhar Bharat is to make India a self-reliant nation. To support the country, he considered the crisis an opportunity and announced 20 lakh crores at the time of the pandemic. He also argued that the package will help the poor, labourers, and migrants in the organized and unorganized sectors of India (Atmanirbhar Bharat Package). It will make the country strong for the competition and lead the country to become an active part of the supply chain at the global level. Make in India was also launched in 2024 to promote manufacturing, investment, and provide job opportunities. Primarily, it started when India's economic growth bent and the country itself faced obstacles in the process of development. Make in India was designed to make our nation a global centre for design and manufacturing (Government of India).

Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana supports unfunded micro enterprises, enabling their economic success and security. The Mudra loan became a beacon of hope for local entrepreneurs and livelihoods, fostering inclusive growth (Mudra 1-2). With this financial aid, many small-scale industries and individuals have taken advantage of new opportunities and are obliged for increased financial stability. During the financial year 2025, 5.53 lakh crores have been sanctioned, and 5.42 lakh crores have been distributed. 5.46 crore loan accounts have benefited, including SC, ST, OBC and women entrepreneurs (3).

Zero Defect Zero Effect was urged to make manufacturing zero defective as well as have zero effect on the environment by the Prime Minister Narendra Modi on the 68th Independence Day (Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises). Behind this idea, there is a vision of

positive impact and quality that has to be maintained if the nation has to maintain its position in the global market.

Support for the International Patent Protection in Electronics and Information Technology scheme, launched by the Department of Electronics & Information Technology, has helped register patents for innovations by individuals or small and large industries. It also helps promote branding, innovation, and secure intellectual property rights (Vats 101).

The Multiplier Grants Scheme was launched by the Department of Electronics and Information Technology to inspire and encourage research and development between academics and industry. Through this scheme, if the industry supports research and development, then the product will be made available for sale, and if any institution supports it, then the government will provide the financial assistance (Multiplier Grants Scheme).

On the eve of Independence Day 2025, Prime Minister Shri. Narendra Modi has introduced the Stand-Up India to promote entrepreneurship at the grassroots level. Primarily, the Stand-Up India scheme was implemented for the upliftment of the weaker sections of society, such as SC, ST and women. According to the scheme, the financial assistance will be provided for manufacturing, agricultural activities and the trading sector with a very low interest rate (Stand-Up India Scheme Features).

The innovation is one of the crucial parts for startups. In the technological advancement era and market competition, startups should have to invent something new to maintain their position, control the market shares and attain growth (Kartika, 46). Through the innovation, the entrepreneurs fulfil the needs of the customers as well as access the space where they can make a new market. Atal Innovation Mission was launched for the innovative ideas of the school,

college and university students. This mission will inspire and create a spirit for innovation. Several kits have been provided under this scheme. Such as 3D printers, robotics, electronics, etc. Through the Atal Innovation Mission, 2900 startups and 3200 job opportunities have been created and have succeeded in creating an innovative environment in India (Vats 102-103). In India, the Government of Gujarat has also implemented a very unique idea, that is the Innovation Club and SSIP (Student Startup and Innovation Policy) at the college level, to generate new ideas among the students and prepare non-technical students for startups through their innovative ideas.

A large number of people who live in rural areas, and rural innovation plays a significant role in the process of problem-solving at the grassroots level, as well as strengthening the rural economy. The rural innovations, such as Water Lifting Device operated by Hand, Groundnut Digger, Paddy Thresher, Tree Climber, Modified Boiler, Bicycle Hoe and Biomass Gasification System (Savkare 99-102). The rural entrepreneurs have faced financial problems, lack of marketing skills and the difficult procedure to get funds. Technological illiteracy and dependence upon the agents from the urban areas lead to slow development. To solve all the difficulties, the rural entrepreneurs should be provided with special training (104).

Women entrepreneurs become an active part of nation-building and succeed in all sectors. Earlier, they were engaged in a very small-scale business like making pickles, papads, powders, cooking, catering, etc. In other words, women are empowered through the small business and self-help groups and in the present time, they are also shaping the financial system of India. Earlier, entrepreneurship was highly male-dominated, but women have changed the mindset after venturing into various fields with innovative ideas (Bhaskar 130).

India is well-known for its initiatives for startups, but there are some obstacles in the process of innovation and startups. Several startups are introduced, but not all succeed and have faced some challenges. Primarily, the lack of infrastructure, such as power, equipment, and good internet connectivity. In the global and local markets, startups are still facing challenges in relation to branding and quality. Social barriers also become hurdles such as caste, class and gender (Vats 104). It is a very tough task to uphold the position in both the global and local markets. Lack of awareness is also one of the significant aspects because there are several innovative ideas that people have, whether they are educated or illiterate.

The innovation and startups unquestionably provide opportunities in various fields. One of the prominent things is that India is the third largest nation in the world and a motivator of new business. More than 50% young people will help to make a perfect platform for the new innovators and new markets that have not been discovered yet (Vats 103). The students who are taking education in the IT, non-technical field and engineering will get a strong platform to present innovative ideas and access various grants for startups. Another thing is that due to the digitalization new opportunities in the field of technology have also emerged, such as payment mechanisms, programming, gaming, and production (103).

The Indian government has started various welfare schemes and programmes for awareness and the upliftment of the rural and urban innovators, and has made them ready to compete at the global level. The pandemic has also provided a strong background to invent something new for the welfare of society. Technological advancement, innovation, knowledge, economic resources, and ventures will make India a self-reliant nation. Over the past

years, India has made a positive impact on the global and local markets. Having plenty of youth power, India will manage to solve the issues of poverty, joblessness and health. The startup culture has definitely succeeded in solving daily problems with limited resources. Finally, the startup culture has created a positive impact on the masses from rural as well as urban areas, whether they are educated or illiterate. Directly and indirectly, the less privileged groups become an active part of nation-building through rural innovation and startups.

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